

AI and the EU skilling challenge

First insights from Cedefop's AI skills survey

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(Cedefop) ([ROR: 03e5p9h20](https://ror.org/03e5p9h20))
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Strengthening skills intelligence for Europe

Cedefop focus

Artificial Intelligence

Survey of **random** samples of (~500) adult workers in 11 EU countries (Feb-May 2024; $n = 5342$)

Better measurement of

- AI use at work
- AI competency/skill gaps
- Automatability of jobs
- Organisational support
- AI outcomes

Cedefop focus

Artificial Intelligence

Cedefop AI skills survey

Algorithmic work powered by AI

About one in seven adult workers usually work with digital tools or apps that can automatically do some tasks, using algorithms.

Source: Cedefop AI skills survey (2024)

Algorithmic work powered by AI

AI in EU workplaces

Another great divergence?

Use of AI at workplace

Increasing use of AI

Source: Cedefop AI skills survey (2024)

Automation or job redesign?

Job automation

highest in routine,
precarious,
middle-skilled jobs
using machines

Fear of job loss due to AI (% all)

Source: Cedefop AI skills survey (2024)

Automation or job redesign?

20%
**of the adult
workforce** believe that
**AI can do more than
a half of their job tasks**

about 23%
of job tasks can be
automated by AI

Automation or job redesign?

AI and task automation

30%

do not do some
tasks any more

67%

do some tasks
faster than before

41%

now do some new
or different tasks

17%

have less control
over job tasks

AI upskilling

Bridging the AI skill gap

61%

will need new knowledge and skills to deal with AI impact on their work

44%

unlikely their company or organisation will provide training to workers to deal with AI

AI upskilling

Bridging the AI skill gap

AI upskilling needs and training

Source: Cedefop AI skills survey (2024)

Prepared for the AI era?

Pillars of AI competency

Source: Cedefop AI skills survey (2024)

Powering the AI transition

Informing VET policies

AI transition = skills transition

Target AI use and upskilling to older,
female workers in SMEs

Improving AI competencies

- Major driver of AI take-up/training
- AI use is skills-based
- AI use less in unexpected work situations/
more in non-procedural jobs

Powering the AI transition

Informing VET policies

Empowering workers

- Organisational support that empowers and not only paralyses with automation fear
- Higher AI training in organisations with staff representation

Tackling the productivity paradox

- AI use associated with higher pay
- For 55% of workers, AI did not improve how to do their job
- Gender segregation (low female use)
- Low AI use/training in lower-skilled jobs

Thank you

For more information

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